

FibreSimulator: An Open-source Python tool for Generating Fiber Phantoms

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Understanding FRPs Starts Inside

- Fiber-reinforced polymers (FRPs) are critical for high-performance industries
- Strength and reliability depend on the **internal fiber structure**
- However, visualizing the internal is **challenging**
- **Tomographic imaging** is the key!

Fiber components: fiber and resin *

> But **high-quality datasets** for developing tomographic algorithms are hard to access!

* Khan, Nazrul & Halder, Sudipta. (2020). Self-healing fiber-reinforced polymer composites for their potential structural applications. 10.1016/B978-0-12-818450-9.00015-5.

Challenges in FRP imaging

- Acquiring high-quality CT datasets is **expensive & time-consuming**.
- Existing datasets are often **private** or **not diverse** enough for algorithm development.
- Existing simulators (e.g., PuMA, TexGen, WiseTex) are **rigid** — limited ability to model different fiber features or scanning conditions.

A Flexible Python Fiber Simulator

Outline

Methods

How *FibreSimulator* builds phantom volumes

Conclusion

Key Takeaways

Experiments

How different parameters affect imaging

Outline

Methods

In real-world X-ray CT scans of FRPs:

- fiber appears as elongated cylinders
- the volume has the material classes:
 - air
 - resin
 - fiber

Fiber components: fiber and resin [1]

Notations & Concepts

- We define a fiber phantom as a set of fibers:

$$\mathcal{P} = \{F_1, F_2, \dots, F_{N_f}\}$$

- Each fiber is a sequence of points:

$$\{p_n\}_{n=1}^{N_s} \subset \mathbb{R}^3$$

- Therefore, a single fiber is written as:

$$F_m = \{(p_1, r), (p_2, r), \dots, (p_{N_s}, r)\}$$

- The total volume is:

$$V_{fibers} = \bigcup_{m=1}^{N_f} V_m = \bigcup_{m=1}^{N_f} \bigcup_{n=1}^{N_s} B(p_n, r)$$

This final equation defines the whole volume as a union of fibers where each fiber is a union of midpoints.

This continuous volume serves as the geometric model of the fiber phantom before discretization.

Voxel Representation

- Once all the fibers are generated in continuous space, they are converted onto voxel grid:

$$V \in \mathbb{R}^{V_x \times V_y \times V_z}$$

where each voxel holds a scalar intensity value [0, 255].

- CT attenuation coefficients: resin, material, air

Given a volume where fibers are growing inside a pipe, a voxel is marked as fiber if its center lies inside any sphere that defines a fiber. Voxels outside the pipe are assigned the air value, while voxels in the pipe that do not contain fibers are filled with resin value.

Single Fiber Generation

a) composition of single straight fiber: **overlapping 3D spheres**

b) **schematic representation** of an axial slice of a fiber phantom

> Why use this design? It offers in **flexibility in choosing** the next point

Since the workflow of building a fiber involves growing it step by step, the user can choose the direction of growth, demonstrating flexibility.

Fiber Phantom Volume Generation

- (1) Start with an empty volume.
- (2) Initialize a starting point.
- (3) Check if the point lies within the volume and ensure that a sphere with the given radius does not overlap with existing fibers.
- (4) Grow the fiber and repeat the process until N fibers are generated.
- (5) Discretize the volume and label the voxels.

repeat until N fibers are generated & fill unoccupied p_i to resin

For the sake of simplicity, we grow a straight fiber in this example, meaning the next point will just be either $+x$ or $-x$ axis.

Fiber Phantom Volume Example

- Real composite materials:
 - wide range of structural variations
 - differences in fiber diameters
 - presence of manufacturing defects
- size of [800 x 800 x 800] showing:
 - hole
 - kinking
 - variation in fiber diameter

Visualization of a reconstructed phantom volume w/ kinking & a hole

Other features

Fiber Orientation, voids

These features are commonly observed in manufactured composites and play a critical role in determining their mechanical performance. To account for this, we incorporated the simulation of these features, aiming to generate more realistic phantoms that reflect imperfections.

Other features

Geometrical Features

These types of features were prioritized for modeling due to the availability of real-world data, enabling qualitative comparison. But because of the flexibility of FibreSimulator, users can generate their own geometrical feature.

Volume & Scanning Parameters

Volume Generation	Tomographic Simulation
# of volumes	# of angles
Volume dimensions	Geometry type
# of fibers	Detector pixel distance
Fiber radius	Detector count
Max. and min. length of fibers	Initial intensity of X-ray beam
Fiber orientation	Reconstruction algorithm
Defects	Distance of source to origin to detector

Detailed description of these parameters can be found on the Github page.

Tomographic parameters from ASTRA toolbox

Outline

Reconstruction Examples

Middle axial slices of increasing # of fibers & increasing voxel radius

These examples demonstrate how the fiber volume fraction (FVF) can be varied in two distinct ways: adjusting # of fibers within a fixed volume (upper row) and altering voxel radius of the fibers (lower row).

Reconstruction Examples

Middle axial slices of increasing # of fibers & increasing voxel radius

FBP

SIRT

Reconstructed middle axial slices of various experimental conditions: 55e3 dose, 50 projections, & 120° limited angular range.

Reconstruction Examples

Real-world data is taken by Zeiss Xradia Vars 520 scanner, conducted with 4 501 projections using a binning factor of 2.

- a) & b) real-world X-ray CT Scans of a carbon FRP
 - estimate the parameters through visualization
- c) & d) generated phantom volume without noise
- e) & f) generated phantom volume with Poisson noise

Comparison of real-world data vs FibreSimulator phantom volume *

Varying tomographic imaging conditions

These are axial reconstruction images of a [256 x 256 x 256] volume acquired using a parallel beam and reconstructed using the SIRT algorithm.

By fine-tuning the parameters in a simulated environment, users can observe their effects on image quality and make informed adjustments.

Comparison of reconstructed middle axial slices at varying **number of projections** (top row) and **noise levels** (bottom row)

With this workflow, it ensures that actual scanning is carried out using an optimized set of conditions.

Varying tomographic imaging conditions

Effect on average diameter & # of fibers detected:

- Decreasing # of projections

As the # of projections decreases, average fiber diameter increases. We can hardly differentiate the boundaries of the fiber, resulting in adjacent fibers appearing fused together.

- Decreasing initial intensity of X-ray beam

A decrease in the initial intensity of the X-ray beam leads to a noisier image. At higher intensities, the average diameter stabilizes close to the ground truth.

Varying fiber characteristics

The rise in error can be attributed to overlapping streak artifacts, which occur when fibers are densely packed.

- Effect of increasing fiber volume fraction (FVF) to the detected # of fibers in a 120° scan
- Interestingly, the error rate follow a non-linear trend w.r.t. FVF

> Showcases the simulator as **flexible & adaptable tool** for studying how sample features affect fiber detectability.

Effect of varying fiber volume fraction on the detected # of fibers

Outline

Conclusions

FibreSimulator is a tool that can assess scanning configurations, establishing its potential as a benchmark for data-driven tomographic algorithms

We **introduced** a simulator that:

- Generates **realistic & customizable** fiber phantoms
- Integrated with **ASTRA toolbox** for CT simulation
- Written in **Python** for flexibility

We **showed** how it can show:

- **relationships** between noise, number of projections, and reconstruction quality
- **impact of fiber density** on fiber detectability

> Future Work: simulation of additional imaging artifacts (source characteristics, beam hardening effects, and detection defect)

Thank you!

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